

Forcrat: Automatic I/O API Translation from C to Rust via Origin and Capability Analysis (Supplementary Material)

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The full list of libc I/O API functions in `stdio.h` is as follows:

```
void      clearerr(FILE *);
char      *ctermid(char *);
int       dprintf(int, const char *restrict, ...)
int       fclose(FILE *);
FILE      *fdopen(int, const char *);
int       feof(FILE *);
int       ferror(FILE *);
int       fflush(FILE *);
int       fgetc(FILE *);
int       fgetpos(FILE *restrict, fpos_t *restrict);
char      *fgets(char *restrict, int, FILE *restrict);
int       fileno(FILE *);
void      flockfile(FILE *);
FILE      *fmemopen(void *restrict, size_t, const char *restrict);
FILE      *fopen(const char *restrict, const char *restrict);
int       fprintf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
int       fputc(int, FILE *);
int       fputs(const char *restrict, FILE *restrict);
size_t    fread(void *restrict, size_t, size_t, FILE *restrict);
FILE      *freopen(const char *restrict, const char *restrict, FILE *restrict);
int       fscanf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
int       fseek(FILE *, long, int);
int       fseeko(FILE *, off_t, int);
int       fsetpos(FILE *, const fpos_t *);
long      ftell(FILE *);
off_t     ftello(FILE *);
int       ftrylockfile(FILE *);
void      funlockfile(FILE *);
size_t    fwrite(const void *restrict, size_t, size_t, FILE *restrict);
int      getc(FILE *);
int       getchar(void);
int      getc_unlocked(FILE *);
int      getchar_unlocked(void);
ssize_t   getdelim(char **restrict, size_t *restrict, int, FILE *restrict);
ssize_t   getline(char **restrict, size_t *restrict, FILE *restrict);
FILE      *open_memstream(char **, size_t *);
int      pclose(FILE *);
void      perror(const char *);
FILE      *popen(const char *, const char *);
int       printf(const char *restrict, ...);
int      putc(int, FILE *);
int       putchar(int);
int      putc_unlocked(int, FILE *);
int       putchar_unlocked(int);
int       puts(const char *);
int      remove(const char *);
int      rename(const char *, const char *);
int      renameat(int, const char *, int, const char *);
void      rewind(FILE *);
int      scanf(const char *restrict, ...);
void      setbuf(FILE *restrict, char *restrict);
int      setvbuf(FILE *restrict, char *restrict, int, size_t);
int      sprintf(char *restrict, size_t, const char *restrict, ...);
int      sprintf(char *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
int      sscanf(const char *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
FILE      *tmpfile(void);
char      *tmpnam(char *);
int      ungetc(int, FILE *);
int      vfprintf(int, const char *restrict, va_list);
int      vfprintf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
int      vfscanf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
int      vprintf(const char *restrict, va_list);
int      vscanf(const char *restrict, va_list);
int      vsprintf(char *restrict, size_t, const char *restrict, va_list);
```

```
int    vsprintf(char *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
int    vsscanf(const char *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
```

Among these, `snprintf`, `sprintf`, `sscanf`, `vsnprintf`, `vsprintf`, and `vsscanf` are pure string operations, and `dprintf`, `renameat`, and `vdprintf` operate on file descriptors.

The following functions require the read capability:

```
int    fgetc(FILE *);
size_t fread(void *restrict, size_t, size_t, FILE *restrict);
int    getc(FILE *);
int    getc_unlocked(FILE *);
```

The following functions require the `bufread` capability:

```
char   *fgets(char *restrict, int, FILE *restrict);
int    fscanf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
ssize_t getdelim(char **restrict, size_t *restrict, int, FILE *restrict);
ssize_t getline(char **restrict, size_t *restrict, FILE *restrict);
int    vfscanf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
```

The following functions require the write capability:

```
int    fflush(FILE *);
int    fprintf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, ...);
int    fputc(int, FILE *);
int    fputs(const char *restrict, FILE *restrict);
size_t fwrite(const void *restrict, size_t, size_t, FILE *restrict);
int    putc(int, FILE *);
int    putc_unlocked(int, FILE *);
int    vfprintf(FILE *restrict, const char *restrict, va_list);
```

The following functions require the seek capability:

```
int    fgetpos(FILE *restrict, fpos_t *restrict);
int    fseek(FILE *, long, int);
int    fseeko(FILE *, off_t, int);
int    fsetpos(FILE *, const fpos_t *);
long   ftell(FILE *);
off_t  ftello(FILE *);
void   rewind(FILE *);
```

The following functions require the close capability:

```
int    fclose(FILE *);
int    pclose(FILE *);
```

Below is the translation of `fflush`:

```
fn fflush<W: Write>(mut stream: W) -> (i32, i32) {
  match stream.flush() {
    Ok(_) => (0, 0),
    Err(_) => (libc::EOF, 1),
  }
}
```

Below is the translation of `fgetc`:

```
fn fgetc<R: Read>(mut stream: R) -> (i32, i32, i32) {
  let mut buf = [0];
  match stream.read_exact(&mut buf) {
    Ok(_) => (buf[0] as i32, 0, 0),
    Err(e) => {
      if e.kind() != ErrorKind::UnexpectedEof {
        (libc::EOF, 1, 0)
      } else {
        (libc::EOF, 0, 1)
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Below is the translation of `fgets`:

```
fn fgets<R: BufRead>(
  s: *mut i8,
  n: i32,
  mut stream: R,
) -> (*mut i8, i32, i32) {
  let buf: &mut [u8] = std::slice::from_raw_parts_mut(s as _, n as _);
  let mut pos = 0;
  while pos < n as usize - 1 {
    let available = match stream.fill_buf() {
      Ok(buf) => buf,
```

```

        Err(e) => {
            return if e.kind() != ErrorKind::UnexpectedEof {
                (std::ptr::null_mut(), 1, 0)
            } else {
                (std::ptr::null_mut(), 0, 1)
            };
        }
    };
    if available.is_empty() {
        break;
    }
    buf[pos] = available[0];
    stream.consume(1);
    pos += 1;
    if buf[pos - 1] == b'\n' {
        break;
    }
}
let res = if pos == 0 {
    std::ptr::null_mut()
} else {
    buf[pos] = 0;
    s
};
(res, 0, 0)
}

```

Below is the translation of `fopen`:

```

fn fopen(pathname: *const i8, mode: *const i8) -> Option<File> {
    let pathname = CStr::from_ptr(pathname as _).to_str().unwrap();
    let mode = CStr::from_ptr(mode as _).to_str().unwrap();
    let (prefix, suffix) = mode.split_at(1);
    match prefix {
        "r" => {
            if suffix.contains('+') {
                OpenOptions::new()
                    .read(true)
                    .write(true)
                    .open(pathname)
            } else {
                File::open(pathname)
            }
        }
        "w" => {
            if suffix.contains('+') {
                OpenOptions::new()
                    .write(true)
                    .create(true)
                    .truncate(true)
                    .read(true)
                    .open(pathname)
            } else {
                File::create(pathname)
            }
        }
        "a" => {
            if suffix.contains('+') {
                OpenOptions::new()
                    .append(true)
                    .create(true)
                    .read(true)
                    .open(pathname)
            } else {
                OpenOptions::new()
                    .append(true)
                    .create(true)
                    .open(pathname)
            }
        }
        _ => panic!(),
    }
    .ok()
}

```

Below is the translation of `fprintf`:

```

fn fprintf<W: Write>(
    stream: W,
    fmt: *const i8,
    args: ...
) -> (i32, i32) {

```

```

    let mut args_0: ::ValistImpl;
    args_0 = args.clone();
    vfprintf(stream, fmt, args_0.as_va_list())
}

```

Below is the translation of fputc:

```

fn fputc<W: Write>(c: i32, mut stream: W) -> (i32, i32) {
    let c = c as u8;
    match stream.write_all(&[c]) {
        Ok(_) => (c as i32, 0),
        Err(_) => (libc::EOF, 1),
    }
}

```

Below is the translation of fputs:

```

fn fputs<W: Write>(s: *const i8, mut stream: W) -> (i32, i32) {
    match stream.write_all(CStr::from_ptr(s as _).to_bytes()) {
        Ok(_) => (0, 0),
        Err(_) => (libc::EOF, 1),
    }
}

```

Below is the translation of fread:

```

fn fread<R: Read>(
    ptr: *mut libc::c_void,
    size: u64,
    nitems: u64,
    mut stream: R,
) -> (u64, i32, i32) {
    let mut buf: &mut [u8] = std::slice::from_raw_parts_mut(ptr as _, (size * nitems) as
    usize);
    let mut i = 0;
    while !buf.is_empty() {
        match stream.read(buf) {
            Ok(0) => return (i / size, 0, 1),
            Ok(n) => {
                buf = &mut buf[n..];
                i += n as u64;
            }
            Err(e) => match e.kind() {
                ErrorKind::Interrupted => {}
                ErrorKind::UnexpectedEof => return (i / size, 0, 1),
                _ => return (i / size, 1, 0),
            },
        }
    }
    (i / size, 0, 0)
}

```

Below is the translation of fseek:

```

fn fseek<S: Seek>(mut stream: S, offset: i64, whence: i32) -> i32 {
    let seek_from = match whence {
        0 => SeekFrom::Start(offset as _),
        1 => SeekFrom::Current(offset),
        2 => SeekFrom::End(offset),
        _ => panic!(),
    };
    stream.seek(seek_from).map_or(-1, |_| 0)
}

```

Below is the translation of ftell:

```

fn ftell<S: Seek>(mut stream: S) -> i64 {
    stream.stream_position().map_or(-1, |pos| pos as i64)
}

```

Below is the translation of fwrite:

```

fn fwrite<W: Write>(
    ptr: *const libc::c_void,
    size: u64,
    nitems: u64,
    mut stream: W,
) -> (u64, i32) {
    let mut buf: &[u8] = std::slice::from_raw_parts(ptr as _, (size * nitems) as
    usize);
    let mut i = 0;
    while !buf.is_empty() {
        match stream.write(buf) {
            Ok(0) => return (i / size, 1),
        }
    }
}

```

```

    Ok(n) => {
        buf = &buf[n..];
        i += n as u64;
    }
    Err(e) => {
        if e.kind() != ErrorKind::Interrupted {
            return (i / size, 1);
        }
    }
}
}
}
(i / size, 0)
}
}

```

Below is the translation of `getdelim`:

```

fn getdelim<R: BufRead>(
    lineptr: *mut *mut i8,
    n: *mut u64,
    delimiter: i32,
    mut stream: R,
) -> (i64, i32, i32) {
    let mut buf = Vec::new();
    match stream.read_until(delimiter as _, &mut buf) {
        Ok(_) => {
            let len = buf.len();
            if len == 0 {
                return (-1, 0, 0);
            }
            buf.push(0);
            if (*lineptr).is_null() {
                *lineptr = libc::malloc(buf.len() as _) as _;
                *n = buf.len() as _;
            } else if buf.len() > *n as _ {
                *lineptr = libc::realloc(*lineptr as _, buf.len() as _) as _;
                *n = buf.len() as _;
            }
            let ptr: &mut [u8] = std::slice::from_raw_parts_mut(*lineptr as _, buf.len());
        };
        ptr.copy_from_slice(&buf);
        (len as _, 0, 0)
    }
    Err(e) => {
        if e.kind() != ErrorKind::UnexpectedEof {
            (-1, 1, 0)
        } else {
            (-1, 0, 1)
        }
    }
}
}
}

```

Below is the translation of `getline`:

```

fn getline<R: BufRead>(
    lineptr: *mut *mut i8,
    n: *mut u64,
    stream: R,
) -> (i64, i32, i32) {
    getdelim(lineptr, n, b'\n' as _, stream)
}

```

Below is the translation of `perror`:

```

fn perror(s: *const i8) {
    use Write as _;
    let mut stream = stderr();
    let _ = if s.is_null() || *s == 0 {
        writeln!(stream)
    } else {
        let s = CStr::from_ptr(s as _);
        if let Ok(s) = s.to_str() {
            writeln!(stream, "{}: ", s)
        } else {
            stream
                .write_all(s.to_bytes())
                .and_then(|_| writeln!(stream, ": "))
        }
    }
};
}

```

Below is the translation of `puts`:

```

fn puts(s: *const i8) -> (i32, i32) {
    use Write as _;
    let mut stream = stdout();
    match stream
        .write_all(CStr::from_ptr(s as _).to_bytes())
        .and_then(|_| stream.write_all(b"\n"))
    {
        Ok(_) => (0, 0),
        Err(_) => (libc::EOF, 1),
    }
}

```

Below is the translation of `remove`:

```

fn remove(path: *const i8) -> i32 {
    let path = CStr::from_ptr(path as _).to_str().unwrap();
    match remove_file(path) {
        Ok(()) => 0,
        Err(e) => {
            if e.kind() == ErrorKind::IsADirectory {
                remove_dir(path).map_or(-1, |_| 0)
            } else {
                -1
            }
        }
    }
}

```

Below is the translation of `rename`:

```

fn rename(old: *const i8, new: *const i8) -> i32 {
    let old = CStr::from_ptr(old as _).to_str().unwrap();
    let new = CStr::from_ptr(new as _).to_str().unwrap();
    rename(old, new).map_or(-1, |_| 0)
}

```

Below is the translation of `rewind`:

```

fn rewind<S: Seek>(mut stream: S) {
    let _ = stream.rewind();
}

```

Below is the translation of `vfprintf`:

```

fn vfprintf<W: Write>(
    mut stream: W,
    fmt: *const i8,
    mut args: VaList,
) -> (i32, i32) {
    let fmt = CStr::from_ptr(fmt as _);
    let mut state = State::Percent;
    let mut flags = vec![];
    let mut width = None;
    let mut precision = None;
    let mut length = None;
    let mut conversion = None;
    let mut count = 0;
    for c in fmt.to_bytes() {
        if state == State::Percent {
            if *c == b'%' {
                state = State::Flag;
            } else {
                match stream.write_all(&[*c]) {
                    Ok(_) => count += 1,
                    Err(_) => return (-1, 1),
                }
            }
        } else if (b'1'..=b'9').contains(c) || (*c == b'0' && state != State::Flag) {
            match state {
                State::Flag => {
                    width = Some(Width::Decimal((c - b'0') as usize));
                    state = State::Width;
                }
                State::Width => {
                    let Some(Width::Decimal(n)) = &mut width else { panic!() };
                    *n = *n * 10 + (c - b'0') as usize;
                }
                State::Precision => match &mut precision {
                    None => precision = Some(Width::Decimal((c - b'0') as usize)),
                    Some(Width::Decimal(n)) => *n = *n * 10 + (c - b'0') as usize,
                    _ => panic!(),
                }
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        - => panic!(),
    }
} else if let Some(flag) = FlagChar::from_u8(*c) {
    flags.push(flag);
} else if *c == b'*' {
    match state {
        State::Flag => {
            width = Some(Width::Asterisk);
            state = State::Period;
        }
        State::Precision => {
            precision = Some(Width::Asterisk);
            state = State::Length;
        }
        - => panic!(),
    }
} else if *c == b'.' {
    if matches!(state, State::Flag | State::Width | State::Period) {
        state = State::Precision;
    } else {
        panic!()
    }
} else if let Some(len) = LengthMod::from_u8(*c) {
    match len {
        LengthMod::Short => match state {
            State::Flag
            | State::Width
            | State::Period
            | State::Precision
            | State::Length => {
                state = State::H;
            }
            State::H => {
                length = Some(LengthMod::Char);
                state = State::Conversion;
            }
            - => panic!(),
        },
        LengthMod::Long => match state {
            State::Flag
            | State::Width
            | State::Period
            | State::Precision
            | State::Length => {
                state = State::L;
            }
            State::L => {
                length = Some(LengthMod::LongLong);
                state = State::Conversion;
            }
            - => panic!(),
        },
        - => {
            length = Some(len);
            state = State::Conversion;
        }
    }
} else if let Some(conv) = Conversion::from_u8(*c) {
    match state {
        State::Flag
        | State::Width
        | State::Period
        | State::Precision
        | State::Length
        | State::Conversion => {
            conversion = Some(conv);
        }
        State::H => {
            length = Some(LengthMod::Short);
            conversion = Some(conv);
        }
        State::L => {
            length = Some(LengthMod::Long);
            conversion = Some(conv);
        }
        - => panic!(),
    }
} else {
    panic!()
}
if let Some(conversion) = conversion.take() {

```

```

let mut opt = std::fmt::FormattingOptions::new();
let mut minus = false;
for flag in flags.drain(..) {
    match flag {
        FlagChar::Apostrophe => panic!(),
        FlagChar::Minus => {
            minus = true;
        }
        FlagChar::Plus => {
            opt.sign(Some(std::fmt::Sign::Plus));
        }
        FlagChar::Space => panic!(),
        FlagChar::Hash => {
            opt.alternate(true);
        }
        FlagChar::Zero => {
            opt.sign_aware_zero_pad(true);
        }
    }
}
if minus {
    opt.align(Some(std::fmt::Alignment::Left));
} else {
    opt.align(Some(std::fmt::Alignment::Right));
}
if let Some(width) = width.take() {
    match width {
        Width::Asterisk => {
            let width = args.arg::<usize>();
            opt.width(Some(width));
        }
        Width::Decimal(n) => {
            opt.width(Some(n));
        }
    }
}
if let Some(precision) = precision.take() {
    match precision {
        Width::Asterisk => {
            let precision = args.arg::<usize>();
            opt.precision(Some(precision));
        }
        Width::Decimal(n) => {
            opt.precision(Some(n));
        }
    }
}
}
match conversion {
    Conversion::Double => {
        if opt.get_precision().is_none() {
            opt.precision(Some(6));
        }
    }
    Conversion::Pointer => {
        opt.alternate(true);
    }
    _ => {}
}
let mut s = String::new();
let mut fmt = std::fmt::Formatter::new(&mut s, opt);
match (conversion, length.take()) {
    (Conversion::Int, None) => {
        let v = args.arg::<i32>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Int, Some(LengthMod::Char)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<i8>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Int, Some(LengthMod::Short)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<i16>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
}
(
    Conversion::Int,

```

```

        Some(
            LengthMod::Long | LengthMod::LongLong | LengthMod::IntMax |
LengthMod::Size,
        ),
    ) => {
        let v = args.arg::<i64>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Int, Some(LengthMod::PtrDiff)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u64>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Int, Some(LengthMod::LongDouble)) => panic!(),
    (Conversion::Octal, None) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u32>();
        if std::fmt::Octal::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Octal, Some(LengthMod::Char)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u8>();
        if std::fmt::Octal::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Octal, Some(LengthMod::Short)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u16>();
        if std::fmt::Octal::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (
        Conversion::Octal,
        Some(
            LengthMod::Long
            | LengthMod::LongLong
            | LengthMod::IntMax
            | LengthMod::Size
            | LengthMod::PtrDiff,
        ),
    ) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u64>();
        if std::fmt::Octal::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Octal, Some(LengthMod::LongDouble)) => panic!(),
    (Conversion::Unsigned, None) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u32>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Unsigned, Some(LengthMod::Char)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u8>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Unsigned, Some(LengthMod::Short)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u16>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (
        Conversion::Unsigned,
        Some(
            LengthMod::Long
            | LengthMod::LongLong
            | LengthMod::IntMax
            | LengthMod::Size
            | LengthMod::PtrDiff,
        ),
    ) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u64>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {

```

```

        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::Unsigned, Some(LengthMod::LongDouble)) => panic!(),
(Conversion::Hexadecimal, None) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u32>();
    if std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&Xu32(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::Hexadecimal, Some(LengthMod::Char)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u8>();
    if std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&Xu8(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::Hexadecimal, Some(LengthMod::Short)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u16>();
    if std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&Xu16(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(
    Conversion::Hexadecimal,
    Some(
        LengthMod::Long
        | LengthMod::LongLong
        | LengthMod::IntMax
        | LengthMod::Size
        | LengthMod::PtrDiff,
    ),
) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u64>();
    if std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&Xu64(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::Hexadecimal, Some(LengthMod::LongDouble)) => panic!(),
(Conversion::HexadecimalUpper, None) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u32>();
    if std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&Xu32(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::HexadecimalUpper, Some(LengthMod::Char)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u8>();
    if std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&Xu8(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::HexadecimalUpper, Some(LengthMod::Short)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u16>();
    if std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&Xu16(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(
    Conversion::HexadecimalUpper,
    Some(
        LengthMod::Long
        | LengthMod::LongLong
        | LengthMod::IntMax
        | LengthMod::Size
        | LengthMod::PtrDiff,
    ),
) => {
    let v = args.arg::<u64>();
    if std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&Xu64(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::HexadecimalUpper, Some(LengthMod::LongDouble)) => panic!(),
(Conversion::Double, None | Some(LengthMod::Long)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<f64>();
    if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
        return (-1, 1);
    }
}
(Conversion::Double, _) => panic!(),
(Conversion::DoubleExp, None | Some(LengthMod::Long)) => {
    let v = args.arg::<f64>();

```

```

        if std::fmt::LowerExp::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::DoubleExp, _) => panic!(),
    (Conversion::DoubleAuto, None | Some(LengthMod::Long)) => {
        let v = args.arg::<f64>();
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&Gf64(v), &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::DoubleAuto, _) => panic!(),
    (Conversion::Char, _) => {
        let v = args.arg::<u8>() as char;
        if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Str, None) => {
        let v = args.arg::<*const u8>();
        let v = CStr::from_ptr(v as _);
        if let Ok(v) = v.to_str() {
            if std::fmt::Display::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
                return (-1, 1);
            }
        } else {
            let v = v.to_bytes();
            match stream.write_all(v) {
                Ok(_) => count += v.len() as i32,
                Err(_) => return (-1, 1),
            }
            state = State::Percent;
            continue;
        }
    }
    (Conversion::Str, _) => panic!(),
    (Conversion::Pointer, _) => {
        let v = args.arg::<*const libc::c_void>() as usize;
        if std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&v, &mut fmt).is_err() {
            return (-1, 1);
        }
    }
    (Conversion::DoubleError | Conversion::Num | Conversion::C | Conversion
::S, _) => {
        panic!()
    }
    (Conversion::Percent, _) => s.push('%'),
}
match stream.write_all(s.as_bytes()) {
    Ok(_) => count += s.len() as i32,
    Err(_) => return (-1, 1),
}
state = State::Percent;
}
}
(count, 0)
}
#[derive(Debug, Clone, Copy, PartialEq, Eq)]
enum State {
    Percent,
    Flag,
    Width,
    Period,
    Precision,
    Length,
    H,
    L,
    Conversion,
}
#[derive(Debug, Clone, Copy, PartialEq, Eq)]
enum FlagChar {
    Apostrophe,
    Minus,
    Plus,
    Space,
    Hash,
    Zero,
}
impl FlagChar {
    fn from_u8(c: u8) -> Option<Self> {
        match c {

```

```

        b'\'' => Some(Self::Apostrophe),
        b'-' => Some(Self::Minus),
        b'+' => Some(Self::Plus),
        b' ' => Some(Self::Space),
        b'#' => Some(Self::Hash),
        b'0' => Some(Self::Zero),
        - => None,
    }
}
}
#[derive(Debug, Clone, Copy, PartialEq, Eq)]
enum Width {
    Asterisk,
    Decimal(usize),
}
#[derive(Debug, Clone, Copy, PartialEq, Eq)]
enum LengthMod {
    Char,
    Short,
    Long,
    LongLong,
    IntMax,
    Size,
    PtrDiff,
    LongDouble,
}
impl LengthMod {
    fn from_u8(c: u8) -> Option<Self> {
        match c {
            b'h' => Some(Self::Short),
            b'l' => Some(Self::Long),
            b'j' => Some(Self::IntMax),
            b'z' => Some(Self::Size),
            b't' => Some(Self::PtrDiff),
            b'L' => Some(Self::LongDouble),
            - => None,
        }
    }
}
#[derive(Debug, Clone, Copy, PartialEq, Eq)]
enum Conversion {
    Int,
    Octal,
    Unsigned,
    Hexadecimal,
    HexadecimalUpper,
    Double,
    DoubleExp,
    DoubleAuto,
    DoubleError,
    Char,
    Str,
    Pointer,
    Num,
    C,
    S,
    Percent,
}
impl Conversion {
    fn from_u8(c: u8) -> Option<Self> {
        match c {
            b'd' | b'i' => Some(Self::Int),
            b'o' => Some(Self::Octal),
            b'u' => Some(Self::Unsigned),
            b'x' => Some(Self::Hexadecimal),
            b'X' => Some(Self::HexadecimalUpper),
            b'f' | b'F' => Some(Self::Double),
            b'e' | b'E' => Some(Self::DoubleExp),
            b'g' | b'G' => Some(Self::DoubleAuto),
            b'a' | b'A' => Some(Self::DoubleError),
            b'c' => Some(Self::Char),
            b's' => Some(Self::Str),
            b'p' => Some(Self::Pointer),
            b'n' => Some(Self::Num),
            b'C' => Some(Self::C),
            b'S' => Some(Self::S),
            b'%' => Some(Self::Percent),
            - => None,
        }
    }
}
}

```

```

struct Xu8(u8);
impl std::fmt::LowerHex for Xu8 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
impl std::fmt::UpperHex for Xu8 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
struct Xu16(u16);
impl std::fmt::LowerHex for Xu16 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
impl std::fmt::UpperHex for Xu16 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
struct Xu32(u32);
impl std::fmt::LowerHex for Xu32 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
impl std::fmt::UpperHex for Xu32 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
struct Xu64(u64);
impl std::fmt::LowerHex for Xu64 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::LowerHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
impl std::fmt::UpperHex for Xu64 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        if f.alternate() && self.0 == 0 && f.precision().unwrap_or_default() == 0 {
            f.write_str("0")
        } else {
            std::fmt::UpperHex::fmt(&self.0, f)
        }
    }
}
struct Gf64(f64);
impl std::fmt::Display for Gf64 {
    fn fmt(&self, f: &mut std::fmt::Formatter<'>) -> std::fmt::Result {
        let v = self.0;
        if v.is_nan() {

```

```

    return f.write_str("nan");
}
if v.is_infinite() {
    return f.write_str(if v.is_sign_negative() { "-inf" } else { "inf" });
}
let sign = if v.is_sign_negative() { "-" } else { "" };
let abs = v.abs();
let p = match f.precision() {
    Some(0) => 1,
    Some(n) => n,
    None => 6,
};
let x = if abs == 0.0 {
    0
} else {
    abs.log10().floor() as i32
};
let s = if x >= -4 && x < p as i32 {
    let frac_prec = (p as i32 - (x + 1)).max(0) as usize;
    let mut s = format!("{:.*}", frac_prec, abs);
    if !f.alternate() && s.contains('.') {
        while s.ends_with('0') {
            s.pop();
        }
        if s.ends_with('.') {
            s.pop();
        }
    }
} else {
    let exp_prec = p.saturating_sub(1);
    let s_full = format!("{:.*e}", exp_prec, abs);
    let idx = s_full.find('e').unwrap();
    let mut mant = s_full[..idx].to_string();
    let exp = &s_full[idx + 1..];
    if !f.alternate() && mant.contains('.') {
        while mant.ends_with('0') {
            mant.pop();
        }
        if mant.ends_with('.') {
            mant.pop();
        }
    }
    let (sign_e, digits) = if let Some(digits) = exp.strip_prefix('-') {
        ('-', digits)
    } else {
        (
            '+',
            if let Some(digits) = exp.strip_prefix('+') {
                digits
            } else {
                exp
            },
        )
    };
    let digits = if digits.len() < 2 {
        format!("0{}", digits)
    } else {
        digits.to_string()
    };
    format!("{e}{f}", mant, sign_e, digits)
};
f.write_str(sign)?;
f.write_str(&s)
}
}

```